

THE METHODOLOGY OF CREATING A REFLECTIVE VIDEO TRAINING ON THE SCIENCE OF "MOTHER LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY" IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract

The article discusses the creation of reflexive video training on the subject "Mother language teaching methodology" in a higher educational institution and the method of increasing the effectiveness of students' professional growth based on reflexive video training. It is envisaged to create reflexive video training in the subject "Methodology of mother tongue teaching" at the higher educational institution and to use reflexive video trainings in the lesson processes in order to optimize the professional growth of students.

Key words: Methodology of mother tongue teaching, methodology, reflection, higher education, mastering, modernization, professional activity, competence, reflexive, creative pedagogy, video training, creation of video training, reflexive experience, result, reflexive experience, person.

Relevance of the issue: Many requirements are placed on the modern educational process. At the top of this list is maintaining the physical and mental health of students. It is necessary to form the educational load, to increase the student's interest in classes and to increase his intellectual potential. Therefore, the word "reflection" is no longer used as a new term. Current reflection is used for various purposes: it examines the impact of student mood not only on the emotional environment, but also on learning activities, process and content. Today, the distinctive feature of state educational standards is their orientation to universal educational efforts, including universal reflection abilities.

In modern pedagogy, reflection means the following: understanding the meaning and method of activity, objective assessment of results, identification of problems.

Individual learning technologies such as the project method, pedagogical laboratories, discussions, research and discussion technologies, problem-based learning, work technology, portfolio technology are based on reflection and can become a full "reflection teacher".

Types of reflection technologies presented by V.A. Metayeva:

Communication methods. They may include methods that are communication-based and involve the author's statement and understanding.

"Interactive". Interactivity implemented in various forms of games and discussions also work as reflection methods.

"Case technology" is a widespread and effective method of analyzing specific situations (English case - random).

"Reflective discussion". Reflexive (in some sources - positional) discussion consists in the fact that one group proposes a project, another suggests alternative ways to optimize it, and the third gives constructive additions to its development.

"Reflective video training" is an effective and widespread method. This significantly increases the efficiency of reflexive processes to ensure personal and professional growth.

"Reflexive game". Reflexive games based on the reflexive method are characterized by introducing participants to democratic behavior, teaching psychotherapeutic relief of group tension, and encouraging deep associations.

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"Reflexive-innovative seminar". To develop the skills of students to organize their activities and interactions in conditions of high uncertainty and inefficiency of previously used tools and systems.

We are talking about reflexive video training, which is one of the above reflexive technologies.

Reflective video training significantly increases the effectiveness of processes that help ensure the personal development and professional growth of trainees. The stages of preparing and conducting reflective video training are traditional and do not differ much from standard training procedures. Let's take a look at them:

preparation of video training - setting the goal, gathering information about the participants, highlighting the main points that will become the object of the video operator and the subject of detailed analysis. The nature of the information about the participants depends on the goals and tasks to be solved during the training. If, for example, the task of developing reflexive skills is set as a component of students' professional competence, then it is important to take into account the level and volume of their professional experience and identify specific personal characteristics that give insight into the tendency of a person to reflect;

developing a scenario that provides the solution to two problems: creating conditions that foster a reflexive environment and "holding" the training topic, which usually deals with situations in professional practice. At this stage, it is important to provide a solution to two problems: to create conditions that foster a reflexive environment and to maintain a training topic that usually deals with situations in professional activity. Two levels of reflection are characteristic for video training: the first is considered at the end of developing the situation according to the scenario, and the second is clarified after watching the video recording of the situation. The discussed stage includes the design of the development dynamics of the group and each student: entering the mode of reflexive activity, reviewing their actions, providing personal and then intellectual reflection, creating a problematic and conflicting situation, developing a mechanism for reflection and using it in the context of specialist difficulties. ability to use.

In the stage of operation and technical equipment of video training, traditional repetition practices are used: for example, the preparation process consists of analyzing the causes of the participant's specific professional difficulties.

The advantage of video training is that participation in it forms a holistic reflexive-developmental environment, if there is co-creation and cooperative relations between participants due to cooperation and individual reflection, this provides an intensive process of self-development and self-awareness. This is a methodology that helps to review one's own experience and develop professional competence.

Figure 1. Stages of preparing and conducting reflexive video training

In higher education, we will consider the process of creating video trainings on the topic "Methods of teaching the sound A and letters Aa to form writing skills in students teaching to write letters" from the subject "Methodology of teaching the mother tongue" in several ways.

In general, the word "Video training" refers to training based on the use of video recordings. Two main methods of video recording are used for educational purposes: showing ready-made video materials (video viewing) and using the recording during the performance of game tasks, viewing and analyzing it (video feedback).

We will consider the method of showing ready-made video materials (video viewing), which is one of the two main methods of video recording for educational purposes, based on the possibilities of using the following issues in the course of the lesson.

The structure of reflective video training includes the following steps:

1. Before the start of the lesson, students are greeted and explanations are given on the topic. The lesson is prepared on the basis of video training, and the students of the group are divided into small groups. The evaluation criteria of the lesson are explained. Evaluation of small groups on the basis of theoretical and practical tasks, and the formation of students' knowledge and skills on the basis of these are explained.

2. To pass the lesson, a video suitable for the problematic direction of the subject to be passed is selected, the main essence of the lesson is determined, and the main content is explained to the

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students based on the video lesson on the subject, oral questions are held to strengthen the subject, and practical tasks are performed:

- statement of the problem - "Teaching to write letters. formation of students' writing skills. Analysis of problems on the topic "Methods of teaching the sound A and letters Aa";
- providing information - "Teaching to write letters. formation of students' writing skills. Getting to know the topic of "A sound and methods of teaching letters Aa";
- practice - "Teaching to write letters. formation of students' writing skills. Using techniques and tools in practical exercises on the topic "Methods of teaching the sound A and letters Aa".

The tools for preparing educational material for video training are selected in accordance with the curriculum.

Figure 2. Scheme of the method of conducting reflexive video training

The procedure for conducting reflexive video training is as follows:

- 1) "Teaching to write letters. formation of students' writing skills. The process of explaining the topic "Methods of teaching the sound A and letters Aa" through a video lesson (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RH7IJptiaL0>) is given below (see Figure 3). While watching this video, students will gain insights into teaching the sound of A and the letter Aa, learn to pronounce, write, reflect on, and observe the Aa teaching activity for discussion.

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Figure 3. Teaching the sound A and the letters Aa

In addition, while watching the video lesson, students create the following key questions for reflective practice:

- Is the correct information given in the video for teaching the sound A and letters Aa?
- What do you think about the pronunciation of the letters aa? Build a psychological portrait of students as you study it.
- Describe the words in the performance of the letters aa? What are these functions associated with?
- Find and show the letter A from the given image in the Aa letter game. Express these in practical terms (see Figure 4).

Such questions can be used by students to learn how to write letters. Formation of students' writing skills. They will not only watch the video lesson on the topic "A sound and methods of teaching the letter Aa", but also learn the ability to analyze and comment on the video.

Figure 4. Aa letter finding game

2) Reflexive processing or discussion of the viewed material, concepts and problem solutions and answering the following questions on the topic:

- How did the video lesson impress you?
- Based on the video lesson, what concepts about the topic made a big impression on you?
- Have you tried learning and writing the letters Aa?

3) Defining the concept of experience and the characteristics of the subject being understood. In the process of discussing the answers to the questions, the students learned to write letters. Formation of students' writing skills. They make a flow chart that tries to figure out all the concepts and what it can lead to on the topic of "A Sound and Ways to Teach the Letter Aa". A logical chain of concepts related to the topic is drawn. Students make predictions about how to get out of these situations.

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4) Modeling. Students will learn about other similar letters, discuss letter concepts, or similar video lessons to understand the relevance of this topic. At the end, students will learn to write letters. Formation of students' writing skills. They develop behavioral standards for learning the topic "A sound and methods of teaching the letters Aa" and implement learning skills for practical work of the basic concepts of the methods of teaching the sound A and letters Aa on the example of a video lesson.

In the same study, "Teaching to write letters. formation of students' writing skills. Similar to the video lesson on the topic "A sound and methods of teaching the letters Aa", video lessons have been prepared on other subjects of the curriculum in the subjects "Native language and reading literacy" and "Mathematics teaching methodology", and video trainings have been organized for each of them.

In short, the methodology of optimizing the professional growth of students based on reflexive video trainings leads to the formation of a kind of technological and pedagogical system based on introducing students to the main features of assertive behavior, technological and communicative interaction of all participants of educational activities, and diagnosing the results of the development process. .

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